

Dielectric Polarisation of *o*-Chloro-, *m*-Chloro- and *p*-Chloro-benzoic Acids in Non-polar Solvents

A. N. SRIVASTAVA*, SUKHVIR SINGH
and
VIRENDRA KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 12 February 1988, revised 23 May 1988,
accepted 6 July 1988

LITERATURE¹ reports apparent dipole moment μ_s of only *m*-chloro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acid in dioxan with a finding that the solvent molecules do not affect the values of μ_s . However, the dielectric measurements carried by us on *o*-chloro-, *m*-chloro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids in dioxan at 35° using a relatively high concentration (10^{-2} – 10^{-3} mole fraction) of the solute reveal that the neglect of the role of dioxan molecules may cause considerable error² in the determination of μ_s values. Consequently, the μ_s values of these acids have been determined by more than one method, viz. Halverstadt and Kunler³ (HKM), Guggenheim⁴ (GM) and Palit⁵ (PM). Results⁶ obtained by a variety of methods show that carboxylic acids are associated in hydrocarbons and similar solvents and that in dilute solutions the associated molecule is dimeric. Also the polar character of various carboxylic acids have been studied in solvents like benzene and heptane by means of measurement of electric polarisation in a very dilute solution. In this context, Brooks and Hobbs¹ pointed out that solvent dioxan is capable to inhibit the association of carboxylic acid molecules and the solvent molecules do not invalidate the μ_s values. However in earlier publications⁷⁻⁹ from this laboratory it has been made clear that a solvent plays very important role in the determination of μ_s and the solvent dioxan possessing a hydrogen bond ability exhibits a specific role in solution.

Such findings have therefore prompted us to remeasure the μ_s value of chlorobenzoic acids, for which we have employed HKM, GM and PM to examine the veracity of the finding reported in the literature¹.

Experimental

Dielectric constant, density and refractive index of several solutions containing different mole fraction of the solute were measured. The method and technique followed were the same as described elsewhere^{10,11}.

All the three acids were procured from Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Bombay. The solvents benzene and dioxan (S. M. Chemical, G.R.) were distilled twice in a quickfit apparatus before use.

Results and Discussion

Literature values for apparent moment μ_s of only *m*-chloro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids in dioxan are based on the assumption that dioxan inhibits the association of carboxylic acids in a high dilution. However, our results at concentrations 10^{-2} – 10^{-3} mole fraction of the solute reveal that the above assumption is concentration-dependent and the μ_s values are much influenced by the dioxan molecules. The recent observation¹² also suggests that the solute–solvent interaction caused by hydrogen bonding increases the μ_s values.

The reason for the μ_s values of *m*-chloro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids in dioxan being observed to be lower, may be due to the neglect of 'solvent effect'. To substantiate this finding the μ_s values have been determined by more than one method. The results are shown in Table 1. The variation of molar polarisation with concentration (Figs. 1 and 2 ;

Fig. 1. Plots of molar polarisation against concentration of 2-chlorobenzoic acid in (O) benzene and (●) dioxan.

Fig. 2. Plots of molar polarisation against concentration of (O) *m*-chlorobenzoic acid and (Δ) *p*-chlorobenzoic acid in dioxan.

TABLE 1—APPARENT DIPOLE MOMENTS IN DEBYE UNIT

Solute	Solvent	μ_H	μ_G	μ_P	Lit. value ^a
Benzoic acid	Benzene	1.37	1.36	1.29	1.61 ^a , 1.70 ^b
	Dioxan	1.86	1.84	1.84	1.76±0.02 ^c
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Benzene	1.74	1.78	1.81	
	Dioxan	4.26	4.24	4.19	
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Dioxan	2.56	2.49	2.77	2.20 ^d
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	Dioxan	3.42	3.24	3.61	2.00 ^d

* Ref. 14, ^bRef. 18, ^cRef. 16, ^dRef. 1.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF MOLAR POLARISATION (P_s) WITH CONCENTRATION (f_s)

<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid in dioxan							
$f_s (\times 10^3)$	1.581 5	2.186 4	2.503 7	3.199 9	3.977 9	7 838 1	10.427 8
P_s	74.04	101.21	135.29	164.09	184.35	248.00	332.25
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid in dioxan							
$f_s (\times 10^3)$	0 225 5	0.869 3	1.072 8	1.550 3	2.147 3	2.448 6	3.543 7
P_s	156.00	127.10	331.18	249.33	195.88	207.5	161.84
<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid in dioxan							
$f_s (\times 10^3)$	0.511 7	0.987 0	1 563 3	2.182 8	2 956 6	3.365 1	4.024 8
P_s	395.78	348.55	318.72	308.51	278.14	256.18	275.41

Table 2) suggests that the observed trend may be arising due to some type of association. On examining the polarisation curve for *m*-chlorobenzoic acid, it is observed that there appears a maxima. This suggests¹³ that the dioxan molecules associate with the acid molecules through hydrogen bonding. It is noticed that the P_s of *p*-chlorobenzoic acid decreases regularly with concentration. This is an indication for an antiparallel association of acid molecules. Similar trend is also reported⁸ in cases of *p*-fluorobenzoic acid in dioxan. It is pertinent to mention that the three polarisation curves are so distinct that they may be used to identify the three isomers. The high apparent moment of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid in dioxan is understandable in terms of incipient ionisation¹³ giving the structure of the form,

The μ_s value of benzoic acid, the parent acid of these solutes, has also been measured both in benzene and dioxan for comparison. The literature values^{14,15} of μ_s for this acid in benzene are widely divergent. We have therefore employed all the three methods mentioned above to evaluate the μ_s value of benzoic acid, which are also listed in Table 1. We find that the μ_s values of benzoic acid in benzene vary considerably from the literature

values, but they are consistent among themselves. It is noted that the literature values besides being divergent appear to be high also. However, in dioxan, the observed μ_s values are in fair agreement with each other and are also comparable with the literature¹⁶ value. The μ_s value of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid both in benzene and dioxan (Table 1) are hitherto unknown. The results presented in Table 3 assist in concluding that $\mu_D - \mu_B$ (μ_D is apparent moment in dioxan and μ_B the apparent moment in benzene) increases with the acidity of the acid.

TABLE 3—APPARENT DIPOLE MOMENT (μ_s)

Solute	Benzene	Dioxan	($\mu_D - \mu_B$)	pK_a
Benzoic acid	1.29	1.84	0.55	4.20
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	1.81	4.19	2.38	2.92

Considering the present results including those reported earlier, it seems that μ_s values of carboxylic acids in the solvents used, depend upon (i) the concentration of the solutions used, and (ii) also on the basic equation employed to evaluate μ_s .

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.K.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship, and the other (S.S.) extends his sincere gratitude to Dr. A. N. Srivastava, Associate Professor, Chemistry Department, University of Jodhpur, for facilities.

References

1. C. S. BROOKS and M. E. HOBBS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2853.
2. A. A. MARYOTT, M. E. HOBBS and P. M. GROSS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1941, 9, 415.
3. I. F. HALVERSTADT and W. D. KUMLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2988.
4. E. A. GUGGENHEIM, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1949, 45, 714.
5. S. R. PALIT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3952.
6. *Quart. Rev.*, 1953, 7, 255.
7. B. KRISHNA and A. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1966, 19, 1847.
8. A. N. SRIVASTAVA and P. R. TALESARA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1976, 49, 1838.
9. A. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil. A*, 1977, 32, 1074.
10. A. N. SRIVASTAVA and P. R. TALESARA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 359.
11. A. N. SRIVASTAVA and V. K. JOSHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, 48, 2942.
12. HILL, VAUGHAN, PRICE and DAVIES, "Dielectric Properties and Molecular Behaviour", Van Nostrand, London, 1969, p. 263.
13. B. KRISHNA and A. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, 37, 1574.
14. H. A. POHL, M. E. HOBBS and P. M. GROSS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1941, 1, 408; C. WILSON and WENZKE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 546.
15. R. J. W. LE FEVRE, R. K. PIERENS and D. V. RADFORD, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1966, 19, 1325.
16. T. FUJITA, K. KOSHIMIZU and T. MITSUI, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 2633.

Phenol-Formaldehyde Cationic Matrices
substituted by Wheat Husk Charcoal

T. DHEIVEGAN** and S. KRISHNAMOORTHY*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College,
Tiruchirappalli-620 015

Manuscript received 11 April 1988, revised 17 June 1988,
accepted 18 July 1988

SYNTHETIC ion-exchangers are used in analytical chemistry, hydrometallurgy and water treatment¹.

Many ion-exchangers owe their origin to petroleum products and there is a continual increase in their cost. It is, therefore, necessary to prepare cheaper exchangers to identify substitutes which

can partly replace the polymeric content of the exchangers to a considerable extent without causing deterioration of the properties of the parent polymers. Attempts have been made in this laboratory² to synthesise newer cationic exchangers from renewable source of materials. The present work is an attempt to prepare and study the properties of sulphonated phenol-formaldehyde cation-exchangers substituted partially by sulphonated charcoal obtained from wheat husk charcoal.

Experimental

Phenol, formaldehyde (B.D.H.), concentrated sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.82) and wheat husk (obtained from local market) were used.

Preparation of the samples: Concentrated H₂SO₄ (12.5 ml) was added slowly to phenol (10 ml) with constant cooling. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 h, cooled immediately in ice and kept overnight. Wheat husk was carbonised and sulphonated by adding concentrated H₂SO₄, heating on a water-bath for about 6 h, washing free from acids and drying at 70° overnight. Calculated quantities of sulphonated wheat husk charcoal were added to phenolsulphonic acid so as to keep the percentage substitution of wheat husk charcoal respectively at 0, 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40. Each mixture was polymerised with formaldehyde (12.5 ml) at 70°, ground and sieved (samples labelled A to F).

A separate sample of sulphonated wheat husk charcoal after purification was subjected to these studies as such (sample G).

Physical measurements: The absolute density of the resin in both the hydrated and dehydrated states was determined by using specific gravity bottle in water and in a non-aqueous medium (toluene), respectively (Table 1).

The gravimetry swelling measurements were made by allowing the samples to equilibrate in water overnight. The weight of the swollen sample (net weight) was taken as M_w and the weight of the corresponding dry sample was taken as M_d . The

TABLE 1 - PERCENTAGE SWELLING, ABSOLUTE DENSITY, ATTRITION PERCENTAGE AND EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF DIFFERENT RESIN COMPOSITES

Sample	Husk-charcoal in resin %	Average swelling %	Absolute density		% Attrition*	Exchange column capacity meq g ⁻¹			
			Hydrated state	Dehydrated state		Na ⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	Zn ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺
A	0	124	1.65	1.51	22.99	0.701	1.137	1.028	1.002
B	20	114	1.50	1.49	21.18	0.694	1.128	1.017	0.994
C	25	97	1.47	1.46	19.17	0.678	1.062	1.014	0.971
D	30	82.5	1.44	1.42	18.80	0.585	0.997	0.914	0.857
E	35	80	1.39	1.33	18.50	0.500	0.865	0.820	0.765
F	40	76.4	1.34	1.22	16.40	0.414	0.748	0.685	0.682
G	100	57.1	1.21	1.12	10.79	0.428	0.438	0.385	0.314

*Amount passed through 200 mesh sieve after shaking.

**Present address: Tamil University, Tanjore.